

Fig. S1 Construction of the VIGS vector.

A) PCR strategy for removal of a fragment of the *AV1* gene in ACMV-[NOg] and insertion of a multiple cloning site (MCS). *CRA*: Common Region of DNA-A; *AV1*: coat protein gene; *AV2*: Protein V2 gene; *AC3*: Replication enhancer protein gene; *AC2*: Transcriptional activator protein gene; *AC1*: Replication associated protein gene; *AC4*: RNA silencing suppressor gene.

B) Cloning steps to generate the VIGS vector and the VIGS-*Chl1* construct targeting the gene encoding the cassava Mg^{2+} -chelataze enzyme (Manes.17G053100).

A

Identities = 144/170 (84%)

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cassava          57 cctgaagaaggggagctcaggccacagctacttgatagatttggaaatgcatgcacaagta 116
N. benthamiana  4160 cctgaagaaggagaacttaggccacaacttcttgatcgatttggaaatgcatgcccaagtg 4219
cassava          117 ggaactgttaaatgctcggagctgagagtgaagatagtgtgaagaaagaggccgttttgat 176
N. benthamiana  4220 gggaccgtgagagatgcagagctgagagtaaatgctgttgaggaaagagctcgttttgat 4279
cassava          177 aaaaaccccaaaagaatttcgtgattcttacaaggcagagcaagagagaagct 226
N. benthamiana  4280 aagaacccaaggaattccgggagctcacaaggcagagcaagagaaaagct 4329

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B**Fig. S2 Validation of the VIGS vector functionality in *N. benthamiana*.**

A) Alignment of the cassava *Chl1* gene (Manes.17G053100) fragment included in the VIGS-*Chl1* construct with the *N. benthamiana* *Chl1* homologue.

http://solgenomics.net/organism/Nicotiana_benthamiana/genome

B) Examples of the VIGS phenotype in *N. benthamiana* targeting the *Chl1* gene.

Fig. S4 VIGS assays targeting the *uidA* gene in transgenic 35S::*uidA* cassava roots. Sterile stem cuttings from VIGS-infected cassava plants were grown in tissue culture and new roots tested for GUS activity after 4 weeks. Phenotypes of three biological replicates for each treatment are shown.

Fig. S5 Silencing in transgenic 35S::*uidA* cassava intermediate and storage roots. VIGS-infected cassava plants in the greenhouse were analyzed for GUS activity in roots six months post-inoculation. Phenotypes of three biological replicates for each treatment are shown.

Wild-type cassava (cv. 60444)

Fig. S6 VIGS assay targeting the *Chl1* gene in wild-type cassava. Examples of plants and leaves showing the silencing of the *Chl1* gene encoding the Mg²⁺-chelataze enzyme (Manes.17G053100). Images were recorded two months post-inoculation. The leaf number is indicated in each case.

Fig. S7 Durability of the *Chl1*-silencing phenotype after grafting and removal of the VIGS vector by thermotherapy.

A) Phenotype of a plant infected with the VIGS-*Chl1* + B construct, one year post-inoculation.

B) Transfer of VIGS-*Chl1* + B from infected rootstock (cultivar 60444) to scion (cultivar BRA222) by grafting.

C) Removal of the VIGS-*Chl1* + B construct by thermotherapy, according to the CIAT method (Mafla et al. 2010). After 4 cycles of thermotherapy (or control *in-vitro* replications), plants were transferred to the greenhouse and photographed.

Table S1. Summary of genetic constructs and infection rates of VIGS vectors. *n* represents the number of inoculated plants.

	Name (size)	Backbone (size)	Insert (size)	Purpose	Infection rate by co-inoculation with DNA-B (<i>Agrobacterium</i> strain used)
A	DNA-A (10,297 bp)	pCambia 1300 (6,407 bp)	DNA-A tandem repeats from the ACMV-NOg isolate (Vanderschuren et al. 2009) (3,890 bp)	Construction of the VIGS vector and used as control in VIGS assays.	Cassava (LBA4404) Assay #1 (n=3): 100% Assay #2 (n=5): 100% Cassava (AGL1) Assay #1 (n=5): 100% Assay #2 (n=3): 100% Assay #3 (n=3): 100% Assay #4 (n=4): 100% Assay #5 (n=3): 100% Assay #6 (n=5): 100% <i>N. benthamiana</i> (LBA4404) Assay #1 (n=4): 100% Assay #2 (n=4): 100%
B	DNA-B (10,283 bp)	pCambia 1300 (6,407 bp)	DNA-B from the ACMV-NOg isolate (Vanderschuren et al. 2009) (3,876 bp)	This plasmid was co-inoculated with the DNA-A or VIGS constructs.	-
C	VIGS-MCS (9,766 bp)	Modified DNA-A: VIGS vector including a Multiple Cloning Site (MCS). (9,766 bp)	Empty VIGS vector. (no insert)	This plasmid was used as recipient plasmid for the below-mentioned gene fragments.	Cassava (LBA4404) Assay #1 (n=5): 0% Assay #2 (n=8): 0% Cassava (AGL1) Assay #1 (n=3): 33% Assay #2 (n=11): 27% <i>N. benthamiana</i> (LBA4404) Assay #1 (n=4): 100% Assay #2 (n=4): 100%
D	VIGS-<i>Chl1</i> (10,214 bp)	VIGS-MCS (9,766 bp)	Middle part of the <i>Chl1</i> first exon (Manes.17G053100) (454 bp)	Silencing of the Mg ²⁺ -chelata- se gene and inhibition of chlorophyll synthesis. Example of VIGS for endogenous genes.	Cassava (LBA4404) Assay #1 (n=4): 0% Assay #2 (n=16): 0% Cassava (AGL1) Assay #1 (n=13): 92% Assay #2 (n=6): 100% <i>N. benthamiana</i> (LBA4404) Assay #1 (n=3): 100% Assay #2 (n=4): 100% Assay #3 (n=4): 100%
E	VIGS-<i>uidA</i> (10,220 bp)	VIGS-MCS (9,766 bp)	5' end of the <i>uidA</i> gene (460 bp)	VIGS assays targeting the coding sequence of the transgene 35S:: <i>uidA</i> in transgenic cassava plants, and control construct for VIGS assays in wild-type plants.	Cassava (AGL1) Assay #1 (n=9): 89% Assay #2 (n=4): 75%
F	VIGS-35S (10,242 bp)	VIGS-MCS (9,766 bp)	-470 > +1 region of the 35S promoter (482 bp)	VIGS assays targeting the promoter of the transgene in 35S:: <i>uidA</i> in transgenic cassava plants.	Cassava (AGL1) Assay #1 (n=6): 100% Assay #2 (n=8): 100%
G	VIGS-71800 (10,260 bp)	VIGS-MCS (9,766 bp)	500 bp fragment of the <i>Manes.12G071800.1</i> targeting exon 1, 10, 11 and 12 (5'end and 3'end of the CDS)	Example of VIGS for endogenous genes.	Cassava (AGL1) Assay #1 (n= 8): 100%

Table S2. Summary of DNA primers.

Name	Sequence (5' – 3')	Purpose
AA/F	ACTGGTGAATGAGTTCCAGACTCGGT	Construction of the VIGS vector
AA/R	TCCAACACGAAATACGGGAAACCC	Construction of the VIGS vector
MCS1	ACTAGTCCCGGGGTACCATGCATGAGCTCA GGTATGTCTGGGCTTCTATACATCCTGTACAT	Construction of the VIGS vector
MSC2	GAGCTCATGCATGGTACCCCGGGACTAGTG ACAGTATTGGCAATTAATAAACATTGAATTTT ATTCA	Construction of the VIGS vector
ACMV-fw	CAA TTT CCA CCC CAA CAT TCA	ACMV (and VIGS constructs) detection
ACMV-rv	GCG TAA GCA TCA TTC GCT GAT	ACMV and (VIGS constructs) detection
Ch11-cDNA fw	TTTTGGGTTCTCGGCGTTTCT	Quantification of <i>Ch11</i> (<i>Manes.17G053100</i>) expression by qPCR.
Ch11-cDNA rv	CATGAAATTGGGACCTCCCTT	Quantification of <i>Ch11</i> (<i>Manes.17G053100</i>) expression by qPCR.
21633 fw	TTGACGACGGTTTCGTGG	Quantification of <i>Manes.12G071800</i> expression by qPCR.
21633 rv	CCGGAGCGGGTACGTAAT	Quantification of <i>Manes.12G071800</i> expression by qPCR.
PP2A-cDNA fw	TGCAAGGCTCACACTTTCATC	Quantification of <i>PP2A</i> (<i>Manes.09G039900</i>) expression by qPCR.
PP2A-cDNA rv	CTGAGCGTAAAGCAGGGAAG	Quantification of <i>PP2A</i> (<i>Manes.09G039900</i>) expression by qPCR.